

Polarographic study of ternary complexes of [Cd^{II}-L-amino acidate-vitamin-PP] system

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Manuscript received 22 June 2007, revised 28 September 2007, accepted 29 September 2007

Abstract : Interaction between Cd^{II} with some L-amino acids such as L-lysine, L-ornithine, L-threonine, L-serine, L-phenylglycine, L-phenylalanine, L-glutamic acid and L-aspartic acid as primary ligands and vitamin-PP (nicotinamide or niacinamide) as secondary ligand has been studied by simple DC polarography using dropping mercury electrode as an indicator electrode and calomel electrode (saturated) as reference electrode at pH = 7.3±0.01 in 1.0 M KNO₃ (supporting electrolyte) at 298 K. Schaap and McMaster method confirmed the formation of 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 complexes with stability constant trend L-lysine < L-ornithine < L-threonine < L-serine < L-phenylglycine < L-phenylalanine < L-glutamic acid < L-aspartic acid can be explained on the basis of nature of amino acids, size and bonding between metal and ligands.

Keywords : Polarography, stability constant, [Cd^{II}-L-amino acidate-vitamin-PP] system.

Introduction

Mostly L-amino acids are blood plasma ligands form stable complexes with various essential metals *in vivo*¹. These L-amino acids are used in many biological processes in human body like transamination, decarboxylation and metabolism. On the other hand, L-amino acids are also involved in intracellular metabolism and operate specific transport systems of the plasma membrane. They do not affect cardiac function under normal conditions². However, there is a growing body of evidence that some of them may be vital for myocardial function and survival during ischemia/reperfusion stress. In this respect glutamic acid and aspartic acid seem to be the most important². Vitamin-PP is water-soluble vitamin B complex, a derivative of niacin. This drug is used in the prevention and treatment of diabetes; it also protects the vital pancreatic cells from diabetes inducing factors³. The niacin nucleotides NAD⁺ (nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide) and NADP⁺ (nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate) serve as coenzymes in a large number of reversible oxidation-reduction systems⁴ also therefore; the metal complexes of these drugs have great importance. Hyperconcentration of transition elements viz. Cd, Zn, Cr, Ni etc. in the blood and serum cause cancer⁵. The concentrations of these metals *in vivo* can be reduced by drug

therapy but the specificity of drug and its amount is stability constant dependent. Therefore, the authors have undertaken the present study to determine the stability constants of ternary complexes with these selected drugs polarographically for which no reference is traced out so far in the literature.

Results and discussion

The overall stability constant of mixed ligand complex species were evaluated by employing Schaap and McMaster method⁷ which confirmed the formation of 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 complexes. All the values of stability constant of [Cd-L-amino acidate-vitamin-PP] system were given in Table 1.

The stability of mixed ligand complexes can be compared with binary complexes to calculate the values of mixing constant log K_m by the following equation,

$$\log K_m = \log \beta_{11} - 1/2 [\log \beta_{02} + \log \beta_{20}]^8$$

The values of log K_m were -0.335, -0.24, -4.865, -0.199, 0.015, 0.11, 0.22 and 0.325 respectively for [Cd-L-lys-vit.-PP], [Cd-L-orn-vit.-PP], [Cd-L-thr-vit.-PP], [Cd-L-ser-vit.-PP], [Cd-L-phg-vit.-PP], [Cd-L-phe-vit.-PP], [Cd-L-glu-vit.-PP] and [Cd-L-asp-vit.-PP] systems. The positive values of log K_m indicate that the ternary complexes are more stable than the binary complexes, while

Table 1. Stability constants of [Cd^{II}-amino acidate-vitamin-PP] system[Cd^{II}] = 0.5 mM, μ = 1.0 M, pH = 7.3 \pm 0.01; temp. = 25 °C

Primary ligand	pK ₂	log β_{01}	log β_{02}	log β_{10}	log β_{20}	log β_{30}	log β_{11}	log β_{12}	log β_{21}
L-Lysine	8.95	-	-	3.70	6.48	9.24	4.27	7.12	9.93
L-Ornithine	8.98	-	-	3.77	6.61	9.42	4.43	7.351	10.16
L-Threonine	9.00	-	-	4.00	7.00	9.50	-	7.47	10.26
L-Serine	9.20	-	-	4.07	7.13	9.69	4.73	7.69	10.48
L-Phenylglycine	9.23	-	-	4.10	7.24	9.71	5.00	-	10.63
L-Phenylalanine	9.30	-	-	4.17	7.37	9.90	5.16	7.83	10.85
L-Glutamic acid	9.67	-	-	4.30	7.45	10.00	5.31	7.93	10.92
L-Aspartic acid	9.82	-	-	4.37	7.38	10.24	5.48	8.15	11.14
Vitamin-PP (nicotinamide)		1.85	2.73						

the negative values indicate that the binary complexes are more stable than the ternary complexes.

The sequence of stability constants is L-lysine < L-ornithine < L-threonine < L-serine < L-phenylglycine < L-phenylalanine < L-glutamic acid < L-aspartic acid. It has been observed that as the size of amino acid increased the stability of complex decreased⁹. The stability of L-lysinate complex is minimum owing to its lowest pK value as compared to rest of the L-amino acids. As the pK value decreases, the stability of complex decreases¹⁰.

In case of L-serine and L-threonine, the stability of the latter is less than the L-serine complex owing to the fact that electron withdrawal OH⁻ group is nearer to L-threoninate complex than L-serinate complex, causing greater repulsive forces between metal and OH⁻ group in L-threonine complexes than L-serine complexes.

As mentioned earlier, as the size of amino acids increases, the stability of complexes decreases. This effect of size on stability was observed in all the selected amino acids except in the case of L-phenylglycine and L-phenylalanine where the order is reversed, i.e. L-phenylglycine < L-phenylalanine. This could be attributed to the presence of phenyl group at α -carbon atom in L-phenylglycine, whereas it is at β -carbon atom in case of L-phenylalanine causing greater repulsive forces in the former than in the latter.

The higher stability of L-aspartate complexes than L-glutamate complex is obvious from the chelate ring formation in these L-amino acids, the L-aspartate forms one five and one six-membered ring with the metal while L-glutamate formed one six and one seven-membered ring¹¹. As the size of ring in L-amino acid increases, the stability of complex decreases. The stabilities of L-glutamate and L-aspartate complexes are greater than those of the L-

lysinate, L-ornithinate, L-serinate, L-phenylglycinate and L-phenylalaninate complexes due to large difference in their basic strength¹². The same is evident from pK values of L-amino acids¹³. A remarkable effect of side chain on the stabilities of complexes have been observed that if the length of side chain in an amino acid increases, stabilities of complexes decrease by a constant factor B^9 . For ternary complexes, the secondary ligand i.e. vitamin-PP (nicotinamide) is same. The stabilities of [Cd(L-glutamate)(vitamin-PP)], [Cd(L-glutamate)₂(vitamin-PP)] and [Cd-(L-glutamate)(vitamin-PP)₂] system are lesser than [Cd-(L-aspartate)(vitamin-PP)], [Cd-(L-asp.)₂-(vit.-PP)] and [Cd-(L-asp.)-(vit.-PP)₂] by a constant factor B , i.e. $\log \beta_{RST11} = 0.17$, $\log \beta_{RST2.1} = 0.2222$ and $\log \beta_{RST12} = 0.2222$, respectively. This order of stability of complexes is applicable to all the selected [Cd-L-amino acids-vitamin-PP] systems. Factor B for ternary complexes are given as :

$$B^9 = \log \beta_{RST} = (C + 4) (i + j) m / 10 (C + 5)$$

where, C is charge on the complex, i , j and m are stoichiometric numbers for primary, secondary and metal ion, respectively $\log \beta_{RST}$ is the reduction factor that gives the reduction in stability for ternary complexes when the side chain in primary ligand i.e. L-amino acid increases by $-\text{CH}_2$. In case of vitamin-PP, N and O of amide group may take part in bond formation with Cd^{II} to form four membered ring¹⁴.

It is clear from the values of stability constant of the complexes that vitamin-PP and amino acids used either singly or simultaneously might be effective to reduce the toxicity of Cd^{II} *in vivo*.

Experimental

The following chemicals were used for all polaro-

graphic experiments : HNO₃ (Sigma), NaOH (Sigma), KNO₃ (Fluka), gelatin (B.D.H.), Cd(NO₃)₂·4H₂O (B.D.H.), L-amino acids (Lobachem) and vitamin-PP (nicotinamide) (Fluka) and their solutions were prepared in double distilled water. The purity of L-amino acids was checked by chromatographic method¹⁵. The concentrations of metal, KNO₃ and gelatin (suppressor) in test solution were 0.5 mM, 1.0 M and 0.001% respectively. Pure nitrogen gas was passed through the analyte for deoxygenation before recording the current-voltage data.

Electrochemical experiment (DC polarography) was carried out using a manual polarograph using a (Toshniwal PL-50) polyflex galvanometer. The polarographic cell was of Latinin and Lingane type in which polarographic capillary of 5.0 cm in length with 0.04 mm in diameter was used. The $m^{2/3}t^{1/6}$ value was 2.40 mg^{2/3} s^{-1/2} at 60.02 cm effective height of mercury. A Systronic pH meter 361 was used to measure the pH of the analyte at 7.30 ± 0.01 adjusted by using dilute solutions of HNO₃ or NaOH as required. Potassium dihydrogen phosphate-sodium hydroxide buffer was added to stabilize the pH of the analyte.

Cd^{II} gave a well-defined two-electron reversible reduction and diffusion-controlled wave in 1.0 M KNO₃ at pH = 7.30 ± 0.01, the value of $E_{1/2}^f$ of Cd^{II} in 1.0 M KNO₃ was -0.586 V vs SCE¹⁶. The plots of log (($i_d - i$)/ i) vs $E_{d.e}$ of Cd^{II} and its complexes gave straight lines with slopes 30 ± 1 mV showing two electron reversible reduction waves. The nature of waves of complexes was also reversible and diffusion controlled.

The concentration of amino acids varied from 0.5 mM to 30.0 mM at two fixed concentration of vitamin-PP i.e. 0.025 M and 0.050 M. It has been observed that $E_{1/2}$ is shifted to more negative side with increase in concentration of L-amino acids.

The depolarizer and ligands (i.e. amino acid and vitamin-PP) were taken in the ratio 1 : 40 : 40 in the case of ternary complexes and current-voltage curves were obtained at different pH values. It has been observed that the maximum shift of $E_{1/2}$ was obtained within the pH range 7.10–8.50, but pH 7.30 was selected for studying the complexes in human blood pH¹⁷.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Head of the Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar for providing the laboratory facilities.

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